

A CASE REPORT ON PSORIASIS VULGARIS WITH KNOWN CASE OF REITERS'S SYNDROME AND PSORIASIS ARTHRITIS WITH SPLEENOMEGALY AND HERPES PROGENITALIS

Priyancy Patel^{1*}, Monil Dabgar¹, Kruti Joshi¹, Dr. S. P. Nayak² and
Dr. G. S. Chakraborty³

¹Department of Pharmacy Practice, Parul Institute of Pharmacy & Research, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

²Department of Pharmacy Practice, Assistant Professor, Parul Institute of Pharmacy & Research, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

³Department of Pharmacy Practice, Principal and Associate Professor, Parul Institute of Pharmacy & Research, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat.

Article Received on
21 October 2022,

Revised on 11 Nov. 2022,
Accepted on 01 Dec. 2022,

DOI: 10.20959/wjpps202212-23809

*Corresponding Author

Priyancy Patel

Department of Pharmacy
Practice, Parul Institute of
Pharmacy & Research, Parul
University, Vadodara,
Gujarat, India.

ABSTRACT

Psoriasis is a chronic autoimmune skin disease with systemic dermatosis characterized by hyperproliferation and inflammation of the skin. Psoriasis Arthritis (PsA) is arthropathy which includes numerous “domains”, such as axial disease, peripheral arthritis, enthesitis, dactylitis, and skin or nail disease. Reiter's syndrome also known as reactive arthritis, is the classic triad of conjunctivitis, urethritis, and arthritis occurring after an infection. Splenomegaly is enlargement of the spleen measured by size or weight. Herpes progenitalis is sexually transmitted infection which is caused by the herpes simplex virus type 2 (HSV-2) or herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1). The patient had multiple disease conditions. Despite on standard therapy with

Methotrexate and topical corticosteroids and other symptomatic relieving agents the patient was unable to recover, leading to disease progression. Hence, it becomes necessary to evaluate the balance between benefits and risks of therapeutic agents, while developing strategies on how to fill up the gaps between characteristics of any individual patient along with presence of complex disease related aspects.

KEYWORDS: Herpes Progenitalis, Psoriasis, Psoriasis Arthritis, Reiter's Syndrome, Splenomegaly.

INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis Vulgaris and Psoriasis Arthritis, (PsA) is a chronic inflammatory arthropathy with a substantial impression on patients' quality of life.¹ Within PsA, there are numerous different "domains" of disease, including axial disease, peripheral arthritis, enthesitis's, dactylitis, and skin or nail disease, which may differ amongst diverse individuals. Psoriasis is a chronic autoimmune skin disease with systemic dermatosis of unknown etiology in which the rate of proliferation of skin cells speeds up and is characterized by hyperproliferation and inflammation of the skin.^[1,2] Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory disease affecting up to 5% of the world's population.^[3] The utmost common manifestations of the disease are, the skin develops raised red lesions which later on, appears as dry scaly patches of silver color. In severe cases, most of the body surface, including the nails and scalp, may be involved.^[2] Reiter's syndrome is also known as reactive arthritis, is the classic triad of conjunctivitis, urethritis, and arthritis occurring after an infection, predominantly those in the gastrointestinal tract or urogenital. Dermatologic indices are common, including keratoderma blennorrhagicum, circinate balanitis, ulcerative uvulitis, nail changes, and oral lesions. The prevalence rate in men's is higher, but cases have been reported in children's and women's too. As the pathophysiology is unclear, but immune factors as well as infectious factors are likely to be involved. Clinical presentation, severity, and prognosis vary widely. Hence, treating the patient becomes difficult, mainly in patients who are HIV positive.^[3] Splenomegaly is defined as enlargement of the spleen measured by size or weight. The spleen plays an important role in hematopoiesis and immunosurveillance. The major roles of the spleen include, removal of microorganisms and antigens, synthesis of immunoglobulin G (IgG), clearance of abnormal erythrocytes. The spleen also synthesizes the immune system peptides namely tuftsin and properdin. Spleen is the reservoir of approximately one-third of circulating platelets. The usual weight of the adult spleen is 70 g to 200 g, spleen weight of 400 g to 500 g designates splenomegaly spleen weight more than 1000 g is conclusive of massive splenomegaly.^[4] Herpes progenitalis is amid the utmost common sexually transmitted infections. It is caused by the herpes simplex virus type 2 (HSV-2) and herpes simplex virus type 1 (HSV-1). Both organisms are enveloped DNA viruses that are sensitive to disinfectants and environmental factors.^[5] Direct contact with the infected person is the primary mode of transmission for both HSV 1 and HSV 2.

CASE REPORT

A 32-year-old male patient presented the complaints of skin lesions over the whole body with multiple erythematous plaques, crusting and silvery white scales on whole body including scalp since one and half months. On examination, multiple erythematous annular plaque with silvery white scaling over margins present over the entire body including scalp, palm, soles and nails displayed subungual hyperkeratosis on left finger nails and dystrophy on right finger nails. Mucosa was still unpretentious.

Treatment History

Pt is k/c/o of Psoriasis Vulgaris since 2017. Pt has admitted in SSG hospital for the same 4 times. (Treated for Reiter's disease in 2017). Pt was on Methotrexate since 2019, taken irregularly. Recently patient was on Tab. MTX (15mg) in Feb'2021.

Past history

P/H/O-Similar complaints since 2016.

Family History

Father having Type-2 DM.

Personal history

Diet: Mixed

Appetite: Decrease

Sleep: Decrease

Bladder: 3-4 times/day

Bowel: 1-2 times/day

Addiction: Alcoholism since 2010, stopped for 1 year, Tobacco chewing since 2010.

General examination

Patient is conscious, Cooperative, Oriented to time, place, person. Patient is examined under proper light and with consent.

Temp- 98 F, B.P.- 108/70 mmHg, Pulse- 93/min, R.R.- 14/min, Spo2-98% on RA.

Cutaneous examination

HEAD AND NECK- Multiple Erythematous plaques over nape of neck with silvery white scales.

FACE AND SCALP- Multiple Erythematous plaques over chin and nape of neck with Silvery white scales and erythematous plaques.

CHEST AND ABDOMEN- Multiple Erythematous plaques over chest and Abdomen with Silvery Scales and Erythematous base over chest and Abdomen. Multiple Hyperpigmented patches over Abdomen and chest.

B/L UL- Multiple Erythematous plaques with Silvery white scales over B/L UL with Erythematous Base.

B/L LL- Multiple Erythematous plaques with Micaceous Scales over B/L LL with Erythematous Base.

BACK AND BUTTOCKS- Multiple Erythematous plaques with crusting Micaceous Scales over Erythematous Base with Multiple Hyperpigmented patches.

PALMS AND SOLES- Multiple Erythematous plaques over Palms and soles.

EXTERNAL GENITALS- Multiple Erythematous plaques with crusting and scales over groin.

NAIL- Dystrophic Changes with onycholysis and onychomycosis of multiple figures and toe nails with subungual hyperkeratosis.

Advice on admission

HPD + 2eggs

TPR/BP/ IO monitoring

Tab. Azithromycin (500 mg) 1 OD

Tab. Methotrexate after Ix

Tab. MVBC / Fe/ FA 1-0-1

Tab. Calcium (500mg) 1-0-1

Betamethasone cream

Clobetasol cream

Liquid paraffin

Topical 3% lotion (Scalp)

Origin, duration and progression

Patient was Relatively asymptomatic before 1.5 months after which he developed multiple Erythematous papules over B/L palms that became pustular and gradually converted into red, raised lesion with peripheral white scales.

Lesions then gradually spread to whole bod and scalp.

Lesions over associated with Body pain, present all times of day, not relieved b medication.

Lesions were associated were B/L knee pain, back pain and inability to walk.

No complaints of Itching, fever, vomiting, Diarrhea before 1 month, breathe lessness, chest pain, Blurring of vision.

The patient was on T.MTX 15mg. Cumulative dose 75m p 60 = 13.5mg. The advice on admission was X-Ray knee, B/L hands. The medications were, T. MTX 5mg 1-1-1 12hrly interval after investigation, T. Azithromycin 500mg 1OD, T. CPM 4mg 1-0-1, T. MVBC/Fe/FA 1-0-1, T. Calcium Gluconate 500mg 1OD, Betamethasone cream LABD, Clobetasol cream LABD, Liquid paraffin LABD (local application twice daily).

PASI score of the patient was 23 which was indicative that the person had severe psoriasis.

PSAI (Psoriasis Area and Severity Index)					
	Head & Neck	Upper Limb	Trunk	Lower Limb	Total
Erythema (0-3)	1	2	2	2	Score 23
Scaling (0-3)	2	2	3	3	
Induration (0-3)	0	0	0	0	
Sum	3	4	5	5	
Surface area					
Involved (1-6)	2	3	5	5	
Sum*Area	6	12	25	25	
Multiplier	0.5	2.4	10	10	

Table 1.1 PASI (Psoriasis Area and Severity Index) is the scale which was developed by British Association of Dermatology. The PASI score is a measurement tool which dermatologists commonly use to assess the severity of psoriasis. It includes the area (parts of body) affected and the intensity. The range of absolute PASI scores is 0–72, with higher scores indicating a greater severity of psoriasis. A score of 0 indicates no psoriasis, while a score greater than 10 suggests severe psoriasis. Using the tool also allows them to monitor the progression of the condition and evaluate the effectiveness of treatment.

Laboratory investigations

Table 1.2: The laboratory investigations included hematology, renal and lipid profile.

The laboratory Investigations (2021)						
01.09.2021 to 07.09.2021	08.09.2021 to 14.09.2021	14.09.2021 to 21.09.2021	22.09.2021 to 28.09.2021	29.09.2021 to 05.10.2021	06.10.2021 to 12.10.2021	13.10.2021 to 20.10.2021
<p>>Hb levels were low ranging between 8.00gm/dL - 9.10gm/dL</p> <p>>Erythrocyte count were low ranging between 3.79 to 4.22 8×10^6 /cmm.</p> <p>>PCV was low 26.30 to 32.40 %.</p> <p>>MCV MCH MCHC were as low as 69, 21, 30.20gm/dL.</p> <p>>RDWcv was increased up to 18.40%</p> <p>>Neutrophils were high 84%, lymphocytes were low 15% and monocytes were 0%</p>	<p>>Sr. ALP 137 high</p> <p>>TIBC RESULTS showed iron levels as low as 22.64μg/dL, TIBC 216.82μg/dL decreased, saturation 10.44%, unbound iron binding capacity 194.18 μg/dL</p> <p>>Levels of Hb, RBC, PCV, MCV, MCH, and monocytes were low, 8.70 gm/dL, 4.13×10^6 /cmm, 28.70%, 70 fL, 30.20gm/dl, 1.00% respectively.</p> <p>>RDWcv18.00%high</p>	<p>>Sr. Total protein and albumin were low 5.80 gm/dL and 3.10 gm/dL respectively</p> <p>>Levels of Hb, RBC, PCV, MCV, MCHC were low, 7.70 gm/dL, 3.83×10^6 /cmm, 26.70%, 68 fL, 20.70 gm/dl, 30.40 gm/dL respectively.</p> <p>>Sr. ALP was increased to 473 U/L</p> <p>>ESR was increased to 150 mm</p> <p>>Reticulocyte count was high 4.00%</p>	<p>>Levels of Hb, PCV, MCV, MCH, and monocytes were low, 9.12 gm/dL, 28.30%, 61 fL, 20.20gm/dl, 1.00% respectively.</p> <p>>RDWcv 23.50% high</p> <p>>Sr. ALP was 483.0 U/L and Sr. Globulin was increased 4.20gm/dL</p> <p>>Potassium was 6.00mEq/L high</p>	<p>>ALP was 333 U/L</p> <p>>Cholesterol was low 113 mg/dL</p> <p>>Levels of Hb, PCV, MCV, MCHC and monocytes were low, 10.20 gm/dL, 34.40%, 66 fL, 29.70 gm/dl, 1.00% respectively.</p> <p>>RDWcv was high 18.00%</p> <p>>Albumin was low 2.90gm/dL Globulin was high 4.30gm/dL</p>	<p>>Sr. Total protein, Albumin and Globulin was high 8.40, low 2.70 and high 5.70gm/dL respectively</p> <p>>ESR was increased to 136.00mm</p> <p>>Levels of Hb, PCV, MCV, MCH, MCHC and monocytes were low, 10.22 gm/dL, 35.45%, 65.26 fL, 18.80 pg 28.83 gm/dl, 1.00% respectively.</p> <p>>RDWcv was high 18.57%</p>	<p>>Levels of Hb, PCV, MCV, MCH, MCHC and monocytes were low, 9.90 gm/dL, 33.30%, 64 fL, 19.20 pg 29.20gm/dl, 1.00% respectively.</p> <p>>WBC were high 11500/cmm</p> <p>>RDWcv was high 17.40%</p> <p>>S. SGPT and S. SGOT were high 123 IU/L and 42 IU/L, S.ALp was high 198 U/L</p>

Other diagnostic tests performed were - Dengue NS1 which was negative and HCV which was negative and Chikungunya IgM test was negative.

RBC morphology remarks stated - RBCs are mildly microcytic, mildly hypochromic, mild anisocytosis, mild poikilocytosis, target cells are seen.

Treatment chart

The treatment was started since 2017, but to due improper medication adherence the disease progressed and then after again the patient came up with same complaints which were severe this time and was treated for the same.

Table 1.3: The treatment profile from 01/09/2021 to 14/09/2021 M/L-multiple, B/L-Bilateral, UL-Upper Limbs, LL-Lower Limbs.

The treatment profile from 15/09/21 to 21/09/21		
PHYSICAL EXAMINATION	ON EXAMINATION	TREATMENT GIVEN
GC: Fair	M/L erythematous annular plaques with micaceous scales & crusting seen over B/L, UL, LL & abdomen, chest, buttocks. Hair & Mucosa were unaffected Nails showed dystrophic changes over M/L fingers and toe nails with subungual hyperkeratosis.	T. Azithromycin 500mg 1OD T. MTX 5mg 1-1-1 at 12 hrly interval on 1 st and 2 nd sept T. MVBC 1-0-1 T. Calcium Gluconate 500mg 1-0-1 Betamethasone cream LABD Clobetasol cream LABD Liquid paraffin LATDS Topical 3% lotion LAHS (Scalp) T. Ketorolac-DT 1-0-1
FC: Pain in B/L		
Temp.: 97.2 F		
Pulse: 91/min		
RR: 13/min		
BP: 110/70 mmHg		
SpO2: 99%		

Table 1.4: The treatment profile from 15/09/21 to 21/09/21 M/L-multiple, B/L-Bilateral, UL-Upper Limbs, LL-Lower Limbs.

The treatment profile from 21/09/21 to 30/09/2021		
PHYSICAL EXAMINATION	ON EXAMINATION	TREATMENT GIVEN
GC: Fair	M/L erythematous annular plaques with micaceous scales & crusting seen over B/L, UL, LL & abdomen, chest, buttocks. Hair & Mucosa were unaffected Nails showed dystrophic changes over M/L fingers – left middle finger showed major changes and toe nails with subungual hyperkeratosis.	T. Azithromycin 500mg 1OD T. MTX 5mg 1-1-1 at 12 hrly interval on 1 st and 2 nd sept T. MVBC 1-0-1 T. Calcium Gluconate 500mg 1-0-1 Betamethasone cream LABD Clobetasol cream LABD Liquid paraffin LATDS Topical 3% lotion LAHS (Scalp) T. Ketorolac-DT 1-0-1
FC: Pain in B/L		
Temp.: 97.2 F		
Pulse: 91/min		
RR: 13/min		
BP: 110/70 mmHg		
SpO2: 98%		

Table 1.5: The treatment profile from 21/09/21 to 30/09/2021 M/L-multiple, B/L-Bilateral, UL-Upper Limbs, LL-Lower Limbs.

The treatment profile from 01/10/21 to 15/10/21		
PHYSICAL EXAMINATION	ON EXAMINATION	TREATMENT GIVEN
GC: Fair	M/L hyperpigmented plaques and patches with papules over the margins of lesions. Hair- few areas of scaling seen in scalp. Nail- dystrophic changes Mucosa- unaffected.	T. Azithromycin 500mg 1OD
FC: Body pain (generalized)		T. MTX 5mg 1-1-1 at 12 hrly interval
Temp.: F		T. MVBC 1-0-1
Pulse: /min		T. Calcium Gluconate 500mg 1-0-1
RR: /min		Betamethasone cream LABD
BP: mmHg		Clobetasol cream LABD
SpO2: 98%		Liquid paraffin LATDS
		Topisal 3% lotion LAHS (Scalp)
		T. Ketorolac-DT 1-0-1

Table 1.6: The treatment profile from 01/10/21 to 15/10/21 M/L-multiple, B/L-Bilateral, UL-Upper Limbs, LL-Lower Limbs.

The treatment profile from 15/10/21 to 30/10/21		
PHYSICAL EXAMINATION	ON EXAMINATION	TREATMENT GIVEN
GC: Fair	M/L hyperpigmented plaques present over B/L for each. M/L erythematous papules seen over margins of plaques Hair- few areas of scaling Nail- dystrophic change + Mucosa- unaffected	Cap. Acitretin 25mg 0-0-1
FC: No		T. Ketorolac-DT 10mg 1-0-0
Temp.: 97.6 F		T. Indomethacin SR 75mg 0-0-1
Pulse: 82/min		T. MVBC 1-0-1
RR: 12 /min		T. Calcium Gluconate 500mg 1-0-1
BP: 122/82 mmHg		T. Tonofolic-Z 1-0-1
SpO2: 98%		Cap. Omez 20mg 1-0-1
		Vit D3 sachet once/week
	Betamethasone cream LABD	
	Liquid paraffin LATDS	
	Topisal 3% lotion LAHS (Scalp)	
	T. Azithro 500mg 10 * 5 days	
	Inj. Cefotaxime 1gm IV	
	T. MTX 15mg wed and thu 7.5mg wed, thu 29,30 10mg wed thu 6,7	
	T. Leucovorin 15mg 1-0-1 * 7 days	
	Cap. Augmentin *7 days	

Table 1.7: The treatment profile from 15/10/21 to 30/10/21 M/L-multiple, B/L-Bilateral, UL-Upper Limbs, LL-Lower Limbs.

The treatment profile from 01/11/21 to 12/11/21		
PHYSICAL EXAMINATION	ON EXAMINATION	TREATMENT GIVEN
GC: Fair	M/L hyperpigmented plaques present over B/L for each. M/L erythematous papules seen over margins of plaques over chest, abdomen, UL, LL. Hair- few areas of scaling Nail-dystrophic change seen on both right- and left-hand nails. Mucosa- unaffected	Cap. Acitretin 25mg 0-0-1
FC: mild bodyache		T. Ketorolac-DT 10mg 1-0-0
Temp.:97.6 F		T. Indomethacin SR 75mg 0-0-1
Pulse: 82/min		T. MVBC 1-0-1
RR: 14/min		T. Calcium Gluconate 500mg 1-0-1
BP: 120/82 mmHg		T. Tonofolic-Z 1-0-1
SpO2: 99%		Cap. Omez 20mg 1-0-1
		Vit D3 sachet once/week Betamethasone cream LABD Liquid paraffin LATDS Topical 3% lotion LAHS (Scalp) T. Azithro 500mg 10 * 5 days Inj. Cefotaxime 1gm IV T. MTX 15mg wed and thu 7.5mg wed, thu 29,30 10mg wed thu 6,7 T. Leucovorin 15mg 1-0-1 * 7 days Cap. Augmentin *7 days

Table 1.8 The treatment profile from 01/11/21 to 12/11/21 M/L-multiple, B/L-Bilateral, UL-Upper Limbs, LL-Lower Limbs.

Summary of the above treatment charts

06/09/2021 – To the physician, R/W/C over p/t Santosh Malivad K/C/O Psoriasis Vulgaris since 2009 in Methotrexate with USG abdomen and pelvis – NAD and chronic alcoholic since 10 ears is having increased liver enzymes.

08/09/2021 – the patient was on MTX and have decreased blood counts

09/09/2021 – to the orthopedic surgoen – swelling in index finger and generalized body pain and ls spine x ray was also done

13/09/2021 – th e patient was kept on hold for MTX treatment due to decreased hb and wbc

14/09/2021 – the mtx on hold, iron sucrose

16/09/2021 – R/W/C THIS PATIENT K/C/O psoriasis vulgaris having C/O neck stiffness and bodyache (not S/O psoriatic arthropathy) patient has no C/O fever, previous dengue. Ns decreased Ag and chikungunya IgM negative orthopedic reference done, all x-rays – NAD

21/09/2021- R/W/C this patient for low Hb – on injection leucovorin 1 ampule in 500ml NS 8 hrly – advice regarding continuation of Leucovorin injection.

27/09/2021 - R/W/C OVER THE PATIENT, S.K⁺ = 6 mEq

28/09/2021 – the patient was on inj. Leucovorin for 6 days T.Vucovorin bd 7 day, inj iron sucrose now Hb - 9.70 gm/dL and MTX – restarting

Discharge Summary

The patient was discharged on 13/11/2021

The PSAI SCORING (before discharge):

Table 1.9: PSAI score is 19 which indicates severe psoriasis. Even after the patient was on therapy for the same there was no major disease cure was seen. The PASI score still indicated that the person was affected severely with psoriasis.

PSAI (Psoriasis Area and Severity Index)					
	Head & Neck	Upper Limb	Trunk	Lower Limb	Total
Erythema (0-3)	1	2	2	2	Score=19
Scaling (0-3)	2	2	2	3	
Induration (0-3)	0	0	0	0	
Sum	3	4	4	5	
Surface area					
Involved (1-6)	2	3	5	5	
Sum*Area	6	12	20	25	
Multiplier	0.5	2.4	6	10	

The diagnostic tests

X-RAY B/L hands, knees, spine was NAD

- X-RAY chest showed no definitive suggestions.
- USG ABD showed splenomegaly 6
- RA FACTOR was negative

The laboratory investigations upon discharge were

Table1.10: The laboratory investigations on discharge, 2022. (The tests performed were: Hematology, liver function tests, Iron binding capacity, Thyroid function tests, Lipid profile, Blood Glucose levels and other tests.

The laboratory Investigations (Discharge, 2022)	
Parameter	Result
Hematology	
Hemoglobin	10.36 gm/dL
White Blood Cells	10,900/cmm
Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate	126 mm
Differential Count	75/23/01/01
Platelet count	32100/cmm
Reticulocyte count 4%	
Liver Function Tests	
S. Bilirubin direct	0.3
S. Bilirubin Indirect	0.5
S. bilirubin Total	0.8
Serum glutamic-oxaloacetic transaminase	
Serum Glutamic Pyruvic Transaminase	
S. Alkaline Phosphatase	
Total Protein	74
Albumin	2.5
Blood tests	
Ferritin	162.70
Total Iron Binding Capacity	216.82
S. Iron	72.64
Saturation	10.44%
Thyroid Function Test	
S. Thyroid Stimulating Hormone	2.4mIU/L
Bl. Urea	52mg/dL
Lipid profile	
S. Triglycerides	44
S. High Density Lipoproteins	29
S. Low Density Lipoproteins	58
Blood Glucose levels	
FBS	90 mg/UL
BS	124 mg/UL
Other tests	
S. HEV	Negative
S.HAV	Negative
HBSAG	Negative
S. WIDAL	Negative
PS FOR CELMOR	Negative
BT GROUP – KOH was wet mount	Negative

Discharge Medications

Rx.

Table 1.11: Discharge Medications.

Discharge Medications				
Sr. No	Drug	Dose	Route	Frequency
1.	Cap. Cyclosporine	50mg	PO	1 OD
2.	T. Methotrexate	2.5mg	PO	2-2-2 at 12hrly interval (wed&thu)
3.	T. Diclofenac	50mg	PO	SOS
4.	T. MVBC		PO	1 OD
5.	T. Tonofolic		PO	1 OD
6.	T. Calcium Gluconate	500mg	PO	1-0-1
7.	Vitamin D sachet		PO	once/week
8.	Liquid paraffin		LABD	BD
9.	Betamethasone cream		LABD	BD
10.	Topical 3% lotion		LABD	BD

Plan: To taper cyclosporine, continue MTX

Diet- high protein diet was advised.

DISCUSSION

DISEASE PROGRESSION

1. Initially, the lesion was seen in the shin area of left leg. The lesion was reddish in color when it emerged and later on the color turned into dark purplish-brown. After few weeks multiple the lesions started appearing over the entire leg and also on the right leg too. The lesions were not painful, the patient had no complaint of fever, cough etc.

Image 1.1: 2017, November.

2. The lesions later on radiated towards the thighs of both the legs and were growing bigger and then after drying and caused scaly patches. The lesions were not painful, they were just emerging and growing in the size after few weeks and later on dries and the marks remained.

When couple of lesions grew up in specific area, it created patch. The patch so formed was painful and causing trouble while sitting and standing. The affected area started itching too.

Image 1.2 2018, January.

Image 1.3 2018, March

3. The lesions later on turned into big patches and started radiating over the specific areas, the patches were too reddish pink in early phase and later on turned out to be dry scaly and purplish brown in color. The patches too gave the burning sensation after hot water baths or when under heavy sunlight.

Image 1.4 2018, July-August.

Image 1.5 2018, December- 2019, January.

The patient did not approach any physician or took the medications regularly initially, later on when the patches started to spread then he consulted a physician.

Due to no adherence towards medication therapy as advised by the physician the condition started worsening. The patient didn't pay much attention to the disease progression and took it lightly. During 2019, the patches started spreading and emerged on the hands, neck and back, scalp and nails.

FROM 2019, January to 2021, December

The emergence of patches and the changes in nails started first in left hand and later on seen in right hand. All the nails of left hand were affected whereas the thumb nail and the ring finger of the right hand were affected. The nails showed dystrophic changes which were progressing too. The wrist to knuckles area was severely affected.

Image 1.5 2019, January.

The entire trunk area was affected and the hands and palms were also affected. He was not able to perform his basic tasks by his own, as he was having continue pain in the hands. (*Image 1.7 & Image 1.8*).

Image 1.9.

Image 1.10

The neck and back were entirely affected. The patient experienced continuous back pain due to which he was not able to stand or sit or perform any activity so he used to just lie on bed and rest (*Image 1.9 and Image 1.10*)

Image 1.11

Image 1.12

Both the legs were equally affected and the nails were showing dystrophic changes too. The left leg was intensely affected as the start of disease was from left leg and later on right leg was affected. The patient was unable to walk normally due to the pain experienced (*Image 1.11 and 1.12*).

CONCLUSION

Despite on the continuous therapy in the last two years the patient was unable to recover. Patient is concurrently receiving doses of Methotrexate, without any clinical outcomes since past thirteen years, while worsening his quality of life. Despite of the continuous therapeutic interventions managing the diseased condition is still challenging. Hence, it becomes necessary to evaluate the balance between benefits and risks of therapeutic agents, while developing strategies on how to fill up the gaps between characteristics of any individual patient along with presence of complex disease related aspects.

REFERENCES

1. Van den Bosch F, Coates L. Clinical management of psoriatic arthritis. *Lancet*, 2018; 391(10136): 2285–94.
2. <https://www.cdc.gov/psoriasis/index.htm>.
3. Ines B Wlu, Robert A Schwartz. Reiter's Syndrome: the classic traid and more. *J Am Acad Dermatol*, 2008 Jul; 59(1): 113-121.
4. Jennifer Chapman; Pankaj Bansal; Amandeep Goyal; Alexandre M. Azevedo. Spleenomegaly, 2021;
5. Nguyen Y, Stirnemann J, Belmatoug N. [Gaucher disease: A review]. *Rev Med Interne*, 2019 May; 40(5): 313-322. [PubMed]
6. King A M Adams M J Carstens E B Lefcowitz E JHrsg. *Virus Taxonomy. Ninth Report of the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses San Diego, CA: Elsevier Academic Press, 2012; 99–124. [Google Scholar]*